

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARL LECHBEN O. GAPUTAN, MPA, LPT

Assistant Professor I
Camiguin Polytechnic State College
nebhcel@gmail.com

“GRYFFYN JOHN”

Gryffyn's the name, mythical creature of old
His story is just starting, it will be unfold
Smart little boy, witty and full of joys
That's who he is now with lots of broken toys

He's sings A-B-C's and counts 1-2-3
Soon do-re-mi will come naturally
He loves Cars, that Lightning McQueen speed
Kung Fu Panda and Moana, fulfilling his need

Watching him grow, a joy to behold
His throne is a chair, and so I'm told
Days fly by fast, now he's almost three years old
Sleeping in bed, unaffected by the cold

Piggy back rides and a burst of laughter
Arla milk with a glass of water
Hugs and kisses from Mama and Dada
Hide and seek with Gryffyn, where is Mama?

Morning breakfasts and a shower bath
Soon he will pave his own path
Me and your mama will always be near
Dry your tears, Gryffyn, we'll always be here

He's still sings A-B-C's and counts 1-2-3
Do-re-mi is coming, so peaceful and free
Ambulance, trucks and trains, his new-found craze
Police cars and airplanes, in a joyful haze